

**CAREER MATURITY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TRIBAL STUDENTS
IN RELATION TO THEIR GENDER**

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Abstract :

This paper is an attempt to study the attitude towards career of secondary school tribal students was selected for the study. Crites Career Maturity Inventory (CMI) and Indian adaptation by Dr. Nirmala Gupta 1989 was administered on the sample to study the Attitude towards career of secondary school tribal students in Odisha. Career Maturity means the individual's ability and readiness to make appropriate career choices. As selection or choice of an occupation is one of the most important aspects among secondary school students it is very essential for the teacher, parents, counselor to know the career maturity. The concept of career maturity is originated from the Supers developmental theory of career behavior and the process of selection of an occupation generally spans from late childhood to early childhood (Dybwad, 2008; Super, 1957). In the study researcher found that as a whole there is a significant difference on the career maturity of secondary school students with relation to the gender.

Keywords: Career Maturity, Gender, Secondary School Tribal Students of Odisha.

INTRODUCTION

Education is means for formation and development of human capacities, attitudes and skills for achievement and realization of the goals of life. The aim of education is to develop the necessary capacities and competencies for facing the challenges of life. The population of Orissa according to the 2011 census stands at about 4.19 million making the 11 most populated states in India. Literacy rate in Orissa has seen upward trend and is 73.45% as per 2011 population census of that male literacy stands at 82.40% while female is at 64.36%. Orissa is treated as 3rd highest ST populated state in India, as per 2001 census. As per 2001 census literacy rate for STs Population in Orissa is 37.4% (Male 51.5% & Female 23.4%).

In spite of various policies adopted by state govt., central govt., NGOs and UNICEF we can find a very significant and drastic change in tribal education. The Orissa government's task force on education, set up to prepare its Vision – 2020 document, presents a gloomy picture of prevailing condition in tribal dominated areas of Orissa. Vision – 2020 document, notes in its report that for three years 27 high schools in the state have showed 'Nil' results which are located in tribal areas.

From the figure, we can see there is a wide difference between the national literacy rate and the literacy rate of the STs of the country. Over the years, the numbers of educational institution have increased in tribal areas, but these are still inadequate student because the number of student seeking enrolment in school is increasing.

Bhargava and Sharma (1995) found inconsistencies in career competencies among high and low achiever of class XII students. The former were higher on career competencies like self and career knowledge, planning and problem solving and latter on goal selection.

Sharma, Bhagarva and Sinha (1993) reported commerce and science students of class XII differing significantly in respect of career attitudes in favor of science group.

Jonson and Asha (1993) studied relationship between self concept, gender, SES and urban-rural set up with career maturity and found no significant relationship of self concept with career maturity emerged; urban female students were higher on vocation maturity than their rural counter parts.

Sundarajan (1993) found no sex differences on the three most preferred occupations by boys and girls at higher secondary stage.

Chander Prabhat (1990) studied educational and vocational interest patterns of tribal high school students and their relationship with intelligence, SES and educational achievement and found that tribal high school boys were higher commerce and medical interest pattern than girls and students belonging to high SES scored high in the mechanical and low in the humanities and arts educational interest patterns of compared to the low SES.

The analysis of the above research studies revealed that less number studies were conducted on career maturity tribal students. In this context studies on career maturity of tribal students is relevant.

Predicting two component of career maturity in school based adolescents- Peter A Creed & Wendypatton (2003) found that self – efficacy, age, career decidedness (certainty) and work commitment were the main predictors of career maturity attitude. Age gender, career decidedness (indecision) were the main predictors of career maturity knowledge.

Wu-Tien Wu, National Taiwan Normal University found that high school students talented in math's and science group, the talented group showing a higher level of career maturity in particular and that there were significant relationships between career variable and academic active good.

The analysis of the above research studies reveled that less number of studies has been conducted and career maturity of tribal students there for present study is an attempt in this direction

Objective of the study:-

The presents study was undertaken to with objectives as recorded under.

1. To study the career maturity of secondary school of tribal students.
2. To find out the difference in the career maturity of secondary tribal students with reference to gender.

Hypotheses:-

Ho1 There is no significant different in career maturity of tribal students with reference to gender

Ho2 There does not exist any significant difference of career maturity of secondary school tribal students, component wise i.e. attitude towards making career choice due to gender variation.

Design of the Study:-

➤ **Sample**

The sample of the presents study 400 tribal high school students (9th & 10th Class) 200 boys and 200 girls from both rural and urban area and govt. & Privet school both was selected by using stratified random sampling taking types of school locality and gender as strata in the district of Sambalpur, Sundargarh, Keonjhar, and Jajpur District of Orissa State.

➤ **Tools**

The investigator administered the following tools to collect the required information

- a. Career maturity inventory (CMI) original prepared by John O' Crites Indian adaptation by Nirmala Gupta

The career maturity inventory (CMI) has been conceived and constructed to measure the maturity of attitudes and competencies that are critical in realistic career decision making. To assess the maturity of these career behaviors, the CMI provides two types of measures: the Attitude Scale and the Competence Test.

Attitude Scale are:

- (i) Decisiveness in career in decision making.
- (ii) Involvement in career decision making.
- (iii) Independence in career decision making.
- (iv) Orientation to career decision making.
- (v) Compromise in career decision making.

The competence Test measures the cognitive variables in choosing an occupation. These include appraisal of the individual's job related capabilities (strengths and weaknesses), knowledge about the world of work, aptness in matching personal characteristics to occupational requirements, foresight in planning for a career and effectiveness in dealing with the problems which arise in the course of career development. In all, then, there are five parts of the Competence Test.

Part-1 – Self Appraisal (SA) (Knowing yourself)

Part-2 – Occupational Information (OI) (Knowing about jobs)

Part-3 – Goal Selection (GS) (Choosing a job)

Part-4 – Planning (PL) (Looking ahead)

Part-5 – Problem Solving (PS) (What should they do?)

➤ **Statistical Techniques Used :**

Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, Standard Error of Mean and Correlation was used for interpretation of the result of the study.

Results and Discussion:

The data is analyzed using various statistical tools for finding the gender difference of secondary school tribal students of Odisha.

Table 1:- Showing the percentage of attitude towards career maturity of secondary school urban tribal students in Odisha with relation to their gender differences

Attitude of Urban Students						
Schools	Gender	Low	Below Average	Average	Above Average High	Schools
Government	Male	20%	18 %	36%	19%	7%
	Female	25%	20%	35%	15%	5%
Private	Male	15%	24%	29%	23%	9%
	Female	20%	32%	25%	18%	5%

From the above table it is clear that out of the Urban Government male students have secured 20% “low”, 18% “below average”, 36% “average”, 19% “above average”, 7% “high” attitude towards their career maturity. Whereas Female students in Government schools have poor attitude towards career maturity compare to the Male students.

Incase of Private school attitude of Male students towards career maturity 15% “low”, 24% “below average”, 29% “average”, 23% “above average” and 9% “high”. Whereas Female students have secured 20% “low average”, 32% “high average”, 25% “average”, 18% “above average”, and 5% “high average”. It signifies that Female students have poor attitude towards career maturity in compare to the Male students of Private schools in urban areas.

Table 2: Showing the percentage of attitude towards career maturity of secondary school rural tribal students in Odisha with relation to their gender differences

Attitude of Rural Students						
Schools	Gender	Low	Below Average	Average	Above Average High	Schools
Government	Male	23%	22%	36%	16%	3%

	Female	29%	23%	32%	15%	1%
Private	Male	19%	24%	29%	23%	5%
	Female	22%	32%	25%	18%	3%

From the above table it is clear that out of the Rural Government male students have secured 23% “low”, 22% “below average”, 36% “average”, 16% “above average”, 3% “high” attitude towards their career maturity. Whereas Female students in Government schools have poor attitude towards career maturity compare to the Male students.

Incase of Private school attitude of Male students towards career maturity 19% “low”, 24% “below average”, 29% “average”, 23% “above average” and 5% “high”. Whereas Female students have secured 20% “low average”, 32% “high average”, 25% “average”, 18% “above average”, and 5% “high average”. It signifies that Female students have poor attitude towards career maturity in compare to the Male students of Private schools in urban areas.

Gender difference in Attitude towards Career Maturity:

Table 3: Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	correlation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	AGB	26.9800	50	9.66688	.641	1.36710
	APB	27.0400	50	8.64955		1.22323
Pair 2	AGG	26.7200	50	9.06899	.847	1.28255
	APG	26.8400	50	8.24710		1.16632

- AGB – Attitude of Government Boys.
- APB – Attitude of Private Boys.
- AGG – Attitude of Government Girls.
- APG – Attitude of Private Girls.

From the above table no 3 it signifies the difference between male and female of secondary school tribal students on Attitude Scale in Government and Private Schools. The obtained Mean of Government Boys Attitude is (26.98) is less than the Attitude score of Private Boys (27.04). In case of Government Girls Mean is (26.72) which is slight less than

attitude of Private school girls student .The obtained SD value of government boys is (9.66)which is better than the private boys tribal school students(8.64).Where as in case of government girls student the standard deviation value is (9.06)compare to (8.24) attitude of private girls students .correlation between government boys and private boys is(.641) , whereas correlation between attitude of government girls and private girls tribal school student is(.847) . it is found that the standard error of mean among the groups are as follows (pair -1) 1.36 and 1.22 in (pair – 2) 1.28 and 1.16 respectively . As a result , null hypothesis which was formulated is rejected because there is a difference of attitude towards career maturity among tribal boys and girls.

From the above results , it can be concluded that the rural boys and girls tribal student have poor career maturity compared to urban tribal students by which they fail to get a suitable job because they do not get proper career guidance or vocational guidance. The tribal students are not well aware about the world of occupation and they are ignorant about different careers available to them in 21st century.

On the basis of population distribution the result indicates that the tribal students belonging to urban area and good socio-economic status have higher career maturity in comparison to rural and low socio-economic status tribal students. Again type of school and the gender is also a great factor which influences the career maturity of tribal students. The career maturity inventory scale is a helpful way for tribal students to gain personal insight into the process of and readiness for making choice in different career which they can opt in their future life. Researcher found from the results that career choice process deals with how individual make decisions, not which occupation they choose.

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